

Research in the field of environmental protection and energy issues

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EDITORIAL

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Editorial

On behalf of the entire Editorial Board, I am very pleased to announce the launch of a new journal called the Journal of Environmental and Energy Science. It is a journal that addresses issues related to environmental technologies and innovations in many industrial areas, with a particular focus on energy. As part of the Journal of Environmental and Energy Science, the publication will cover the following areas of environmental and energy transition technologies, technologies improvements, energy efficiency, environmental protection, energy sources, storage, and applications, energy and environmental transition, sustainable development, energy conversions, fundamentals, and buildings, economy and policy aspects on energy and environment, energy usage and savings.

In today's world, ecology, as well as environmentally friendly technologies, play an important role. Their use is influenced by a wide variety of factors. The results of studies [1] show that the application of restrictive pro-environmental policies, the introduction of environmental taxes, as well as the development of pro-environmental technologies, are influencing greater interest in the use of renewable energy sources. Of course, this process is a long one, and various factors influence energy innovations that limit the use of fossil fuels. However, successfully implemented innovations can in turn contribute to reducing environmental pollution, including greenhouse gas emissions into the atmosphere. Certainly, a transition toward a cleaner environment requires appropriate environmental management at production facilities. In turn, at national levels, changes toward the introduction of cleaner technologies require the restructuring of environment-related policies to introduce incentives for citizens to abandon outdated solutions that negatively affect the environment in favor of using cleaner energy sources. As shown in [1], taxing all polluting activities will not only discourage pollution but also improve environmental quality in the long run. Of course, it is important to have real incentives that can influence, if not in the short time horizon, then in the longer period, the implementation of the modernization strategy in companies.

We are observing a growing environmental awareness among the public, which is why progress related to research in the field of clean energy technologies, as well as other solutions that can have an impact on improving environmental quality, is so important.

Available research [2] indicates that the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, which have a negative impact on the climate, is influenced by factors such as the production of electricity from renewable sources, as well as ecological innovations. Industrialization, on the other hand, has an impact on increasing greenhouse gas emissions, hence the transformation towards technological change, mainly in the energy sector, is recommended to counteract the negative effects of climate change.

Modeling of various scenarios using carbon capture and utilization, in which carbon dioxide is captured from the atmosphere and used to produce synthetic fuels that can replace fossil fuels, has indicated clear advantages in minimizing changes in energy demand sectors such as transportation, however, it has also been pointed out that the technology is cost-intensive compared to existing scenarios, and that it is based on a technology still in development [3].

The high cost of technologies can reduce companies' incentives to implement them. Research results show [4] that government subsidies can serve as an effective way to reduce the financial burden on companies to improve technology. In

addition, government subsidies are conducive to expanding the market for green products and improving social welfare.

The ongoing energy transition requires the involvement of various sectors in more efficient use of resources. The continuous evolution of industrial operations and productivity requires the development and implementation of energy efficiency measures [5]. However, choosing the right technology for a specific industry that is acceptable in terms of cost remains a major challenge for many companies.

We hope that the publications contained in this journal will be useful and interesting to our readers and will influence pro-environmental decision-making. For the authors of the publications, the journal will at the same time become a useful channel for the distribution of research results, which, given the above, are of great importance to many societies.

Types of articles, objectives, and scope

The new open-access journal, established under the title of Journal of Environmental and Energy Science, is an international peer-reviewed open-access journal, which allows readers to access the content of the articles free of charge, and consider for publication articles covering all the areas described above. We highly encourage academic authors from around the world to publish their research results in this journal. All articles undergo

a thorough review process to ensure the highest quality of published content for readers.

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Conflict of interest

The author declares no conflict of interest

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References

- [1] Xiaoyan Niu, Zhili Zhan, Baoqi Li, Zhenling Chen, Environmental governance and cleaner energy transition: Evaluating the role of environment friendly technologies, *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments*, Volume 53, Part C, 2022, 102669, ISSN 2213-1388, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2022.102669>.
- [2] Fengsheng Chien, Ka Yin Chau, Muhammad Sadiq, The effect of energy transition technologies on greenhouse gas emissions: New evidence from ASEAN countries, *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments*, Volume 58, 2023, 103354, ISSN 2213-1388, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2023.103354>.
- [3] Ken Oshiro, Shinichiro Fujimori, Tomoko Hasegawa, Shinichiro Asayama, Hiroto Shiraki, Kiyoshi Takahashi, Alternative, but expensive, energy transition scenario featuring carbon capture and utilization can preserve existing energy demand technologies, *One Earth*, 2023, ISSN 2590-3322, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2023.06.005>.
- [4] Rui Yang, Wansheng Tang, Jianxiong Zhang, Technology improvement strategy for green products under competition: The role of government subsidy, *European Journal of Operational Research*, Volume 289, Issue 2, 2021, Pages 553-568, ISSN 0377-2217, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2020.07.030>.
- [5] M Abdullah M. Maghrabi, Jian Song, Christos N. Markides, How can industrial heat decarbonisation be accelerated through energy efficiency?, *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 2023, 121092, ISSN 1359-4311, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2023.121092>.